

**THE PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AND ITS EFFECTS ON BODY IMAGE AMONG
UNDERGRADUATES AT OSUN STATE UNIVERSITY, MAIN CAMPUS, OSOGBO,
OSUN STATE**

SUBMITTED BY

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**A PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
BACHELOR OF SCIENCES (B.SC.) IN PUBLIC HEALTH**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project work titled '**THE PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AND ITS EFFECTS ON BODY IMAGE AMONG UNDERGRADUATES AT OSUN STATE UNIVERSITY, MAIN CAMPUS, OSOGBO, OSUN STATE**', is my original work and has not been submitted elsewhere for any academic award. All sources consulted have been duly acknowledged.

ADEWOLE ADEBOLA VICTORIA

DATE

2021/34124

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work titled '**THE PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AND ITS EFFECTS ON BODY IMAGE AMONG UNDERGRADUATES AT OSUN STATE UNIVERSITY, MAIN CAMPUS, OSOGBO, OSUN STATE**' was carried out by Adewole Adebola Victoria with the matriculation number of 2021/34124 in the Department of Public Health, Faculty of Basic medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, Osun State University, Osogbo, under the supervision of Dr. Akin Ajayi. The work meets the requirements for the award of a Bachelor of Science degree in Public Health.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to the memory of my late father, Mr. Oluwatoyin Adewole, whose biggest dream was to see me graduate from the university. Though he is not here today to witness this milestone, his love, vision, and sacrifices continue to inspire me. This work is a fulfillment of his dreams and a tribute to his legacy.

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I am deeply grateful to God Almighty for His grace, wisdom, and strength which have sustained me throughout this project.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BMI- Body Mass Index

NCDs - Non-Communicable Diseases

WHO- World Health Organization

EOSS- Edmonton Obesity Staging System

UNIOSUN- Osun State University

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Obesity is a growing public health concern linked to physical and psychological effects, including negative body image among young adults. This study examined the prevalence of obesity and its effects on body image among undergraduates of Osun State University, Osogbo.

AIM: This study was designed to focus specifically on assessing how prevalent obesity is among the students and to investigate its impact on the body image.

METHODOLOGY: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 210 undergraduates selected using stratified random sampling. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and anthropometric measurements. BMI was calculated by dividing weight by the square of height to classify weight status. Data were analysed using SPSS version 27.0, with results presented in tables and figures.

RESULT: The prevalence of obesity was gotten as 12.4%. The result showed that obesity was associated with lower body confidence and increasing clothing avoidance, with significant p-values of 0.0018 and 0.0137, respectively. Other variables, including self-esteem, self-consciousness, pressure to look a certain way, and social participation, showed no significant associations.

CONCLUSION: This study showed the prevalence of obesity is rising in this population group and this may lead to increase in the burden of non-communicable diseases linked to obesity.

Obesity among undergraduates in Osun State University is associated with not only physical health risks but influences how students view and interact with their bodies.

There is a gap in education regarding obesity and its effects on body image perception.

WORD COUNT: 252

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Obesity is a condition of abnormal accumulation of fat in the adipose tissue, to the extent that health may be impaired. Obesity is a growing public health problem globally, affecting people of all ages and socioeconomic backgrounds. It can be prevented, corrected and improved. It is measured with body mass index greater than or equals to 30kg/m². Obesity is not just an underlying factor for major chronic diseases, it is also a serious debilitating condition on its own (Ehwarieme et al., 2024).

Obesity was coined from two Latin words 'ob' which means excess and 'edere' which means eat. It depends mainly on lifestyle factors, such as low rate of physical activities, frequent intake of fast foods and chronic overeating. (Safaei et al., 2021)

Overweight and Obesity contribute to numerous chronic non-communicable diseases (NCDs) worldwide. (Bray et al., 2017)

The consequences of obesity have been documented extensively in connection with Non-communicable diseases (NCD) like cardiovascular diseases, type II diabetes mellitus, dyslipidaemia, and certain types of cancers, such as the hormonal-related (breast, ovarian, endometrial, and prostate), liver and large-bowel cancers, and gallbladder disease, known for their morbidity and mortality (Hildebrand & Pfeifer, 2025). Also, the non-fatal but debilitating

health problems associated with obesity include respiratory difficulties, chronic musculoskeletal problems, skin problems and infertility (world health organization 2018).

Although, obesity and overweight were once considered problems of high-income countries, a rapid increase in obesity rates have also been documented in the developing world. Until recently, the report shows that a steadily increasing trend of obesity among young adults is becoming evident (Rafei et al.2022).

The contributing factors to obesity include age, gender, ethnicity, culture, food habits, lifestyle, and lack of physical activity. The increased supply of processed food, rapid urbanization and changing lifestyles has led to a shift in dietary patterns leading to the global burden of obesity. Evidence shows that the highest percentage of college students who consume fast foods are in the obese group(Shah et al., 2014).

The pressures of university life, including academic stress, peer influence, and busy schedules, contribute to poor dietary habits and reliance on easily accessible junk foods.(Abraham et al., 2018). Furthermore, studies revealed that university students had a low daily intake of fruits and vegetables, frequently engage in snacking habits and had a higher frequency of fast-food consumption, thereby promoting dietary behaviour that can lead to unintended weight gain(Erndt-marino et al., 2022)

University students are at increased risks of having obesity due to the adoption of unhealthy lifestyles and school related stress. However, there is a few information regarding the prevalence and risk factors of obesity among students in Osun state University, main campus Osogbo.

Among undergraduate students, which mainly represent the young adult population group, poor lifestyle habits, including decreased quality of diet and physical activity, sedentary lifestyle, alcohol use and smoking, as well as decreased quality sleep, are associated with obesity(Mogre et al., 2014) Also, the concurrence of altered eating behaviours (emotional eating, uncontrolled eating, and restrained eating), depression and poor sleep are estimated to be high among undergraduate students, mainly females(Amoako et al., 2023).

Although there were many studies targeting the undergraduates' pattern of nutrition, their knowledge and perception of obesity as the major risk factor for NCDs have not been fully explore(Ghazali et al., 2021).

Therefore, it is of utmost importance to assess how much undergraduates know about obesity and its related conditions, their perception of it and the influence of their knowledge on their dietary

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

University students are at increased risks of having obesity due to the adoption of unhealthy lifestyles and school related stress.(Al-dalaeen et al., 2024).

Obesity can be exacerbated by reducing sleep by just two to three hours per night, according to (Alhamlan et al., 2025).However, there is a few information regarding the prevalence and risk factors of obesity among students in Osun state University, main campus Osogbo

Undergraduate obesity rates are rising, yet many students are not well informed about the risks. Studies on undergraduate students' attitudes, knowledge, and behavioural reactions to obesity are still scarce, despite the fact that public education campaigns have been proposed as a successful strategy to reduce obesity-related NCDs like psychological illness. Developing focused solutions requires an understanding of students' knowledge of obesity, the problems it poses, and how their attitudes affect their eating habits(Diana et al., 2023)

Furthermore, several comprehensive reviews have suggested that between 20% and 60% of persons with obesity, and extreme obesity in particular, suffer from a psychiatric illness such as such as depression, low self-esteem, and body image dissatisfaction have been linked to obesity(Aucott et al., 2014).

Additionally, it is suggested that obese individuals gradually become depressed due to their negative body image, low quality of life, and other physical consequences (JA et al., 2018). In this regard, Brewis and Han proposed some logical findings, arguing that obesity and its concerns influence depressive symptoms in individuals(Brewis et al., 2017)

Thus, this study will help to determine and identify the prevalence of obesity and its effects among undergraduates in Osun State University, Main Campus, Osogbo, Osun state.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Obesity is incurring substantial costs for healthcare that are already affecting the society. Obesity can be prevented, avoided, and cured. Prevention of obesity is the best policy, but proper treatment is necessary for those that are already affected with obesity. (Mohajan & Mohajan, 2023).

This study relates directly to SDG 3's goal of ensuring healthy lives and promoting wellbeing for all.

Understanding the effect of obesity on the body image among undergraduates is crucial for creating targeted interventions to support their overall wellbeing(Yiyi et al., 2024).

With the rise in the rate of obesity among young adults, universities, health organizations, policymakers need evidence based strategies to improve health lifestyles, psychological wellbeing and effective weight management among undergraduates of Osun State University, main campus, Osogbo (Plotnikoff et al., 2015).

This study will investigate growing public health issue, the increase in the prevalence of obesity among students, which requires urgent attention. It will highlight the impacts of obesity on the psychological status of undergraduates, which are often not looked into compared to its impact on physical health.

The study will create insights into students' knowledge and perceptions of obesity which can help shape effective awareness campaigns and health interventions (Styk et al., 2024)

Additionally, this study will help to contribute to existing literature by filing the research.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the prevalence of obesity among undergraduates in Osun state university, Main campus, Osogbo university?
2. What are the effects of obesity on body image among undergraduates?
3. What are the coping mechanisms used by undergraduates in managing obesity and concerns related to obesity?

1.5 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.5.1 General objective

The chief objective of this research is to investigate prevalence of obesity and its effects on body image among undergraduates at Osun state university, main campus, Osogbo, Osun state

1.5.2 Specific objectives

1. To determine the prevalence of obesity among undergraduates.
2. To identify effects of obesity on body image among undergraduates.
3. To identify coping mechanisms used by undergraduates in managing obesity and concerns related to obesity.

1.6 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

1.6.1 Null hypothesis (H₀)

There is no significant relationship between obesity and the body image of undergraduates in Osun state university, main campus, Osogbo.

1.6.2 Alternative hypothesis (H₁)

There is a significant relationship between obesity and the body image of undergraduates in Osun state university, main campus, Osogbo.

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

- At the end of this study, we will be able to explore and understand the effects of obesity on the body image on undergraduates
- This study will help health professionals to develop targeted interventions to tackle mental health issues related to obesity
- This will also educate students and the community about the mental health risks associated with obesity.

1.8 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is designed to focus specifically on assessing how prevalent obesity is among the students and to investigate its impact on the body image.

This study will also explore undergraduates' dietary patterns, lifestyle habits, physical activities and their awareness and coping mechanism related to obesity.

1.9 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERM

(a) Obesity: it is the condition that occurs when a person's body has an excess amount of fat.

Obesity is caused by an imbalance of energy intake(diet) and energy expenditure (physical activities)

In most cases obesity is a multifactorial disease due to obesogenic environments, psychosocial factors and genetic variants(Who, 2015)

(b) Body mass index: it is a numerical value derived from a person's weight and height, used as a simple index to classify underweight, overweight and obesity(Classification et al., 2021)

(c) Psychological status: it is the mental and emotional wellbeing of a person. It includes how individuals feel about themselves, relate to others and make choices.

(d) Coping mechanism: these are the strategies individuals use to manage stress, emotional challenge etc. In this study, coping Mechanisms include things like exercise, dieting, counseling and social support.

(e) Psychological supports: These are any professional or emotional assistance given to improve mental health.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPT OF OBESITY

World Health Organization defines health as “an abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that may impair health” and “the fundamental cause of obesity and overweight is an energy imbalance between energy consumed and energy expended” (WHO,2016).

Obesity is a complex, expensive, chronic and non-communicable disease shaped by various factors, including lifestyle habits, stress, health conditions and medications, genes and people’s environment. Recognizing these risks help individuals and communities to take steps to prevent and reduce obesity. (Risk Factors for Obesity | Obesity | CDC, n.d.).

Excess weight gain is often unintentional and gradual, and it is sometimes difficult to reverse without an individual’s commitment or will. It is recorded as the fifth foremost reason for global mortality. It is considered the “New life syndrome” that reduces life expectancy.(Mohajan & Mohajan, 2023)

Most people are obese because the energy intake in their diet has over a period, exceeded their energy output, in metabolism, movement and growth(Gurneya & Gorsteinb, n.d.)

2.2 MEASUREMENT OF OBESITY

There are different means through which obesity can be tested for, the most widely-used method is Body Mass Index (BMI).

BMI is calculated as weight in kilograms divided by the height in metres squared. In adults, overweight, or pre-obesity, is defined as a BMI of 25-29.9 kg/m², while a BMI \geq 30 kg/m² defines obesity.

Other methods of classifying obesity include measurement of waist circumference, waist to hip ratio and the Edmonton Obesity Staging System (EOSS).

Waist circumference is an easy and non expensive method. It is a reasonable indicator of intra-abdominal or visceral fat. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence cut off points suggest males with WC >94cm or Females with WC => 85cm are considered to be at increased risk of obesity.

Waist to hips ratio highlights if excess weight is stored around the waist. Males with a waist to height ratio >1.0 and Females with a weight to height ratio >0.85 are considered to be at increased risk.

2.2.1 Edmonton Obesity Staging System-Staging tool

Edmonton Obesity Staging System (EOSS) is a novel risk-stratification system that classifies obese individuals into five graded categories, based on their morbidity and health-risk

profile. EOSS focuses on how obesity is affecting someone's life. It ranks severity of obesity based on clinical assessment of weight-related health problems, mental health and quality of life.(Hellbardt et al., 2017) (Abdelaal et al., 2017).

STAGE	CLASSIFICATION
0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No obesity related health issues • No sign of obesity risk factors • No physical and psychological symptoms • No functional limitations or health problems
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mild obesity related health issues • At this stage, the patient obesity related subclinical risk factors such as hypertension mild sleep problem, impaired fasting glucose and mild joint pain etc.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate obesity related health conditions • At this stage, the patients have established • obesity related comorbidities like type 2 diabetes, sleep apnea, Polycystic ovary Syndrome, reflux diseases etc that requires medical interventions. • Moderate obesity-related psychological symptom such as depression, eating disorders, anxiety disorders etc • Limits to physical and daily functions
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant obesity related complications • At this stage. the patient has established • Significant obesity-related end-organ damage like heart diseases, kidney disease diabetic complications, incapacitating osteoarthritis etc) • Significant functional limitations like reduced mobility, inability to complete routine activities
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Severe, disabling obesity related problems • This is the potential end stage. At this stage, the patient has severe disabling psychological symptoms and severe functional limitations. The person may be bed ridden or require full time care

Table 2.1 Edmonton Obesity Staging System -Staging tool

2.2.2 Body Mass Index classification of obesity by World Health Organization

BMI is used to define and diagnose obesity according to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines.

CLASSIFICATION	BMI
Underweight	<18.50
Normal weight	<18.50-24.99
Pre obese	25.00-29.99
Obese (class 1)	30.00-34.99
Obese (class 2)	35.99-39.99
Obese (class 3)	40.00 and above

TABLE 2.2: BMI Classification

2.3 DETERMINANTS OF OBESITY

2.3.1 Dietary factors

Unhealthy diets contribute to obesity basically by creating a positive energy balance, where calorie intakes constantly exceed calorie expenditure. Diets high in energy-dense, nutritious poor foods such as sugar-sweetened beverages, refined carbohydrates, and food high in saturated fat are digested rapidly, leading to rise in blood glucose and insulin and it promotes storage of fat(*TheLancet*, n.d.)

2.3.2 Genetics

Genetic factors play a huge role in the development of obesity, influencing appetite regulation, energy expenditure, and fat distribution. (Loos & Yeo, 2022) noted that genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have identified more than 1000 genetic loci associated with body mass index (BMI), with many located in genes expressed in the central nervous system, particularly those involved in hypothalamic regulation of hunger. Rare monogenic form of obesity can lead to severe, early obesity, while common polygenic obesity results from the combined effect of multiple genetic variants interacting with environmental factors.

2.3.3 Gender

Research indicates that women have a higher risk of having obesity than men. Higher obesity among women compared to men could be driven by several factors, including sex differences in psychological responses to early-life nutrition, pregnancy-associated weight gain combined with higher parity, hormonal changes, physical activity levels, depression, sociocultural factors such as the perception of ideal body size and beliefs surrounding acceptability of physical activity and postpartum weight retention (Ford et al., 2017)

2.3.4 Socioeconomic and Environmental Factors of Obesity

Epidemiological studies have examined how geographical, social, and cultural factors contribute to obesity. These factors often profoundly shape dietary habits and behaviours, leading to unhealthy dietary patterns in certain populations. For instance, individuals with lower awareness of proper nutritional practices may be more susceptible to obesity (Ogden et al., 2017)

Socioeconomic status (SES) has played a huge role in the rise of obesity. Study found an association between low income and obesity. Similarly, several studies have purported that wealth is inversely related to obesity. In a systematic review and meta-analysis aimed at identifying the relationship between income and obesity reported that earning a low income was associated with obesity. The possible explanation for the finding of obesity being prevalent among the lowest income cadre may be that the low-income earners constitute the urban poor. Financial constraints may therefore cause them to opt for meals high in dense carbohydrates to achieve satiety as opposed to healthy fruits, vegetables, and proteins which are expensive in the urban areas. (Ugochukwu et al., 2015) The financial constraint to healthy food leads to disparities in obesity prevalence across different communities. These disparities are closely tied to social determinants of health, e.g., limited access to physical activity opportunities, wholesome dietary options, and general health education. (Keyes et al., 2025).

2.3.5 Physical inactivity

Physical activity accounts for the greatest variation in total energy expenditure. Adults with physical or mental disabilities are more likely to be obese; those with reduced lower-extremity mobility are at the most significant risk. Lack of physical activity and increased sedentary behaviour have been linked to an increased risk of obesity. (Piercy et al., 2021).

According to a World Health Organization survey, more than 28% of the world's adult population and 81% of adolescents were physically inactive in 2016. Increasing use of passive modes of transportation have led to reduced physical activity.

2.3.6 Insufficient sleep

Sleep regulates glucose metabolism and neuroendocrine function. Lack of sleep reduces glucose intolerance, insulin sensitivity and leptin levels and increases the levels of cortisol and ghrelin (and, therefore, appetite). One study also found that a change in the mean duration of sleep increased the risk of obesity by modifying the effects of fat mass and obesity-associated gene variants on BMI (Hruby et al., 2016)

2.4 PREVALENCE OF OBESITY

2.4.1 Prevalence of obesity globally

Globally, there is increasing prevalence of obesity in both developing and developed countries. Obesity rate has increased in developing countries by three over the last 20 years as these countries become more urbanized, with rise in the consumption of high calorie food and adoption of more inactive lifestyle. (Peltzer et al., 2015)

Obesity is considered a principal public health concern and ranked as the fifth foremost reason for death globally (Safaei et al., 2021). The problem of obesity is a major contributor to the global burden of chronic disease and disability, with serious social and psychological implications that affect virtually all ages and socioeconomic groups. (Haththotuwa et al., 2020).

In 2015, 107.7 million children and 603.7 million adults were obese worldwide. The overall prevalence of obesity for adults was 12.0% respectively globally (Gates et al., 2015).

2.4.2 Prevalence of obesity in Africa

A meta-analysis conducted by (Tulp et al., 2018) on adult obesity among 48823 individuals in Africa reported that the prevalence of obesity is 21.8% among adults across the continent. The study highlighted that urbanization and lifestyle patterns as the major contributing factors of obesity. As many urban dwellers have shifted towards many sedentary routines and diet high in sugary and processed foods. In addition to that, the study also stated that cultural beliefs and norms also contribute to the rising trend of obesity in many Africa societies.

2.4.3 Prevalence of obesity in Nigeria

A recent systematic review and meta-analysis by (Ijezie et al., 2022) examined 33 population studies involving 37,205 adults across Nigeria to estimate the national prevalence rate of overweight and obesity.

	Prevalence (%)
Nationwide	
Obesity	14.5
Geopolitical zone	
North-central	10.2
North-east	6.4
North-west	10.4
South-east	15.7

South-west	13.9
South-south	24.7

Table 2.3 Prevalence of obesity in Nigeria

2.5 UNIVERSITY STUDENTS AND OBESITY: A GROWING CONCERN

Undergraduate obesity is a developing public health issue that frequently manifests during the time spent in college, when lifestyle choices are being formed. More than one in twenty students were obese, with prevalence rates of 5.8% for men and 5.2% for women, according to a large cross-sectional study conducted by (Peltzer et al., 2014), which involved 15,686 students aged 16 to 30 (mean age 20.8) from 22 universities in low-, middle-, and emerging-economy countries.

University students are more likely to become obese because of their altered lifestyles and mental burdens, Academic pressure, growing independence, financial strain, and exposure to poor eating habits are some of the unique problems that come with being a student at a university. Many students acquire weight as a result of dietary changes, decreased physical activity, and unpredictable sleep habits(Oftedal et al., 2024).

2.6 PROGRESS ON OBESITY PREVENTION

According to (Roberto et al., 2015) In 2023, the member states of the World Health Organization(WHO) adopted the Global action plan for the Prevention and Control of Non-communicable Diseases, 2013-2020, along with its framework. The obesity target within the monitoring framework: No increase in the prevalence rate from 2010 to 2025. Similarly, WHO's

strategy for improving maternal, infant and young children feeding aims to prevent any increase in obesity prevalence among children. Yet achieving even this low bar represents a significant challenge and will require urgent, coordinated efforts from governments and broader range of stakeholders to meet global non-communicable diseases prevention goals.

2.7 CONCEPT OF BODY IMAGE

Body image is an individual's perspective, thoughts, and feelings regarding their body. It is a multifaceted, dynamic, and subjective term. (Neagu, 2015). Concerns about one's body image include obsession with and discontent with one's physical attributes, such as weight and shape. Due to intense pressure to meet appearance standards, body image issues are prevalent worldwide (Rodgers et al., 2023)

2.8 BODY IMAGE DIMENSIONS

2.8.1 Perceptual dimensions: According to (Grogan et al., 2016), cultural and societal influences, including the ideals of beauty propagated by the media, peers, and family, have a significant impact on how people perceive their bodies

2.8.2 Cognitive dimensions: The cognitive part of body image encompasses internal thought processes, ranging from positive beliefs like body admiration and functionality recognition to negative evaluative beliefs like feelings of inadequacy concerning looks (Quittkat et al., 2019)

2.8.3 Behavioural dimension: Body image-related behaviours, such as body checking and avoidance, are among the most obvious indicators of underlying discontent and can reinforce a negative self-image. Similar coping methods, avoidance behaviours such as avoiding mirrors,

tight clothing, or social settings where the body is on display, contribute to a vicious cycle of negative perception and mental anguish(Nogueira & Betanho, 2012)

2.8.4 Affective dimensions is an individual's emotional experiences with their body, which can range from good emotions like pride and satisfaction to negative ones like shame, remorse, and worry, (Raider, 2023).

2.9 RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN OBESITY AND BODY IMAGE

(Mohamed, 2023) concluded that Participants who were obese have a significantly increased risk for poor body image perception A healthy body image doesn't only affect students' self-esteem and satisfaction but also their overall mental health. poor body image is associated with reduced quality of life and performance necessitating proper interventions.

2.10 GENDER DIFFERENCES IN BODY IMAGE CONCERNS

(Breda-vicentini & De-bortoli, 2020) examined how male and female university students perceives body image relative to actual representations using a custom Scale of Silhouettes. It revealed that female students consistently selected silhouettes with higher values compared to male students indicating greater dissatisfaction or distortion in body image perception among women. The findings suggest that socially accepted beauty standards continue to exert a stronger negative influence on women's body image than men's, affecting how they perceive both themselves and others

2.11 CONSEQUENCES OF NEGATIVE BODY IMAGE

2.11.1 Psychological consequences

Body image concern in individuals leads to psychological distress. (Arzeen, 2021) explored how body image correlates with psychological distress among university students, finding that students who were dissatisfied with their bodies reported significantly higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms. The results suggest that negative perceptions of body image are closely linked to deteriorating mental health among undergraduates, emphasizing the importance of psychological and counselling support interventions on campus to address these challenges.

2.11.2 Academic and social implications (withdrawal, isolation)

Negative body image isn't just a mental health issue; it can also affect a student's academic and social life. For instance, (Li et al., 2024) Psychology study among Chinese college students found that social withdrawal was linked to negative body image, and this relationship was further influenced by alexithymia (difficulty identifying or expressing emotions). In turn, this combination often led to problematic social media use, which can further isolate students from real-life interactions.

2.11.3 Risk behaviours (disordered eating, extreme dieting)

A study of Kuwaiti male university students found An unrealistic desire among Kuwaiti college men to increase muscle mass as well as drastically decrease body fat was related to the risk of disordered eating attitudes, Participants who wanted to reduce body fat or increase muscle had higher odds of exhibiting such behaviours (Ebrahim et al., 2019)

Body image dissatisfaction has been associated with poor nutritional status and unhealthy weight management strategies. Among undergraduates in Lagos, Nigeria, body image dissatisfaction was notably high (63.5%). Nearly all respondents engaged in weight management practices, with 37.7% reporting strict dieting as the most common and often unhealthy strategy(Olatona et al., 2023).

2.12 COPING MECHANISMS FOR OBESITY AND BODY IMAGE CONCERNS

2.12.1 Healthy coping (physical activity, peer support)

Peer support appears to be associated with decreased weight and BMI levels in individuals with obesity(Chen *et al.*, 2021) .A comprehensive meta-analysis found that engaging in physical exercise significantly improves body esteem in female participants. Notably, aerobic exercises alone or combined with resistance training, had the most substantial impact on enhancing body satisfaction(Zhang *et al.*, 2024)

2.12.2 Role of family, peers, and institutional support

A 2022 research shows that college students' physical activity behaviours are significantly influenced by support structures: school-based support (like access to facilities) has the strongest impact, followed by peer encouragement, and then family support, often mediated by students' self-efficacy (Zhang & Zhang, 2022)

2.13 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.13.1 Social comparison or Body comparison

This is the process of comparing one's own look to that of others by examining their physical characteristics and associated traits. According to the social comparison theory, people are naturally motivated to assess their own beliefs, skills, development, and position in society (Laker & Waller, 2022). The theory consists of people's biological drive for self-evaluation, skill, and overall identity compared to others based on what they know about others (*Instagram Ideals: College Women's Body Image and Social Comparison*, n.d.)

2.13.2 Objectification theory emphasizes how internal body surveillance and shame brought on by societal objectification eventually affect eating habits and mental health (Schaefer et al., 2019)

2.13.3 Sociocultural theory

According to sociocultural theory, young people's body dissatisfaction is fuelled by their continuous exposure to Westernised body ideals, especially on social media (Çınaro & Yilmazer, 2025).

2.13.4 Self-Discrepancy Theory

(Möri et al., 2022) uses images to gauge how people perceive actual vs ideal media in media. Results show that Facebook and YouTube shape body ideals perceived to be prevalent in the media, negatively influencing internalization and self-discrepancy. Self-discrepancy, in turn, increases body dissatisfaction.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

The study was carried out at Osun State University, Main Campus, Osogbo (UNIOSUN) located in Osun State, Nigeria. UNIOSUN is a multi-campus public university established by the Osun State Government in 2006.

The main campus has two colleges including College of health sciences and college of science, engineering and technology.

The choice of the university has the study area is based on its accessibility, diverse in students' population and relevance to the study topic. The institution provides a suitable environment for academic, social, and physical development, making it suitable for this study.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study employed was a descriptive cross sectional study design because data was collected at a single point in time.

3.3 TARGET POPULATION

For the study on ‘The prevalence of obesity and its effect on body image among undergraduate in Osun State University, Main Campus Osogbo’, the target population includes all the undergraduates enrolled in Osun State University across all the campuses.

3.4 STUDY POPULATION

For the study on, ‘The prevalence of obesity and its effect on body image among undergraduate in Osun State University, Main Campus Osogbo’, the study population, the subset of target population, includes all undergraduate students enrolled at Osun State University, Main Campus, Osogbo

3.4.1 Inclusion Criteria

- Enrollment status: Must be a currently enrolled undergraduate student at Osun State University, Main Campus, Osogbo.
- Psychological Assessment: Must be willing to complete body image status evaluation

3.4.2 Exclusion criteria

- Pregnant Students: Pregnancy can influence BMI and psychological status
- Medical Conditions Affecting Weight: Individuals with known medical conditions that significantly impact weight (e.g., thyroid disorders, genetic conditions).

3.5 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

To determine the required sample size, Cochran’s formula was used

$$n = Z^2P(1-P)/ e^2$$

where:

$Z = 1.96$ (for a 95% confidence level)

$P = 0.145$ (prevalence of obesity in Nigeria = 14.5% (Ijezie et al., 2022), "Prevalence of Overweight and Obesity in Nigeria").

$e = 0.05$ (margin of error = 5%)

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.145 * (1 - 0.145)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 190.5$$

Rounding up:

$$n = 191$$

Required sample size = 191 undergraduates

Adding 10% for non-response rate

$$\text{Therefore } n = 191 + 19.1 = 210.1$$

3.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Stratified random sampling technique was used because the population is divided into strata like colleges, faculties, departments and levels and it ensured a fair representation of each group.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

A self-structured questionnaire was used for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire will be divided into 4(four) sections;

SECTION A: Sociodemographic characteristics

SECTION B: Obesity related information

SECTION C: Effects of obesity on body image

SECTION D: Coping mechanisms and support system

A mechanical weighing scale was used to take weight measurements before the completion of the questionnaires. Weight was measured to the nearest 0.5kg (kilogram) using a calibrated scale. Measuring tape was used to measure the height of the participants in meter (m)

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Data were entered, cleaned, and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize sociodemographic characteristics, anthropometric measurements, physical activity, dietary habits, family history, and lifestyle factors.

The prevalence of obesity was calculated as the proportion of participants with a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m². BMI was calculated as the weight in kilograms divided by the height in meters squared (kg/m²).

3.8.1 Outcome variable (dependent variable)

These were the variables measured to assess the body image status of the students. It was measured through indicators self-confidence, self esteem etc.

3.8.2 Scoring variable (independent variable)

This was measured using Body Mass Index (BMI). BMI is calculated dividing weight (kg) by the square of height(m).

3.9 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical permission was sought and obtained from the research ethics committee in Osun State University to conduct this study (UNIOSUNHREC 2025/PBH/128).

Consent was obtained from each participant before data collection commenced. Participation in this study was entirely voluntary, and confidentiality of all information provided was strictly maintained.

3.10 LIMITATION OF STUDY

This study has several limitations. Firstly, it was conducted in a single university, which may not fully represent the experiences of undergraduates in other institutions.

Secondly, the study employed a cross-sectional design, meaning data was collected at a single point in time. This limited the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships between obesity and psychological status.

Also, BMI does not distinguish the difference between body fat percentage and lean body mass (i.e., muscle). It overestimates body fat in muscular persons and underestimates it in less muscular persons.

Finally, other potential factors influencing both obesity and mental health, such as genetic predispositions, socioeconomic status, and lifestyle habits, was not extensively explored.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

TABLE 4.1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY(n=210)	PERCENTAGE (%)
AGE IN CATEGORIES		
16-19	101	48.1
20-23	94	44.8
24-27	15	7.1
Mean=19.79(SD=2.299)		
GENDER		
Male	69	32.9
Female	141	67.1
Others	0	0
LEVEL OF STUDY		
100	75	35.7
200	57	27.1
300	25	11.9
400	52	24.8
Others	1	0.5
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	202	96.2
Married	6	2.9
Others	2	1.0
What is your average monthly allowance or income		
Less than #10000	31	14.8
#10000-#30000	77	36.7
#31000-#50000	49	23.3
Above #50000	53	25.2

Table 4.1. summarized the sociodemographic characteristics of 210 undergraduates that participated in the study. The largest proportion of the respondents were within the age of 16-19 years (48.1%), followed closely by those aged 20-23 years (44.8%), while the smallest proportion were aged 24-27 years (7.1%). A larger percentage of respondents were female subjects (67.1%) and (32.9%) were males. The majority were in 100 level (35.7%), with a smaller proportion in 300 level (11.9%). 96.2% of the respondents were single. In terms of monthly allowance or income, (36.7%) earned between ₦10,000 and ₦30,000, while (14.8%) earned less than ₦10,000. This demographic distribution provides the necessary background for understanding obesity patterns among the respondents.

TABLE 4.2: OBESITY RELATED INFORMATION

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n=210)	PERCENTAGE (%)
BMI (kg/m²)		
Underweight	30	14.3
Normal weight	106	50.5
Overweight	48	22.9
Obese	26	12.4
 HOW OFTEN DO YOU CHECK YOUR WEIGHT?		
Weekly	11	5.2
Monthly	29	13.8
Occasionally	75	35.7
Rarely	80	38.1
Never	15	7.1
 DO YOU CONSIDER YOURSELF OBESE?		
Yes	13	6.2
No	197	93.8
 HAVE YOU EVER TRIED		

TO LOSE WEIGHT?

Yes	60	28.6
No	150	71.4

**HAVE YOU EVER BEEN
DIAGNOSED WITH
OVERWEIGHT OR OBESE
BY A HEALTHCARE
PROFESSIONAL?**

Yes

No	15	7.1
	195	92.9

**DO YOU HAVE ANY
FAMILY HISTORY OF
OBESITY?**

Yes	23	11.0
No	187	89.0

TABLE 4.2 This study shows that Most participants in this study have a normal weight (50.5%), while 35.3% are above normal weight (22.9% overweight and 12.4% obese) and 14.3% are underweight. Despite this, very few (6.2%) consider themselves obese, and only 28.6% have attempted to lose weight, showing a gap between actual weight and perception. Weight monitoring is infrequent, with the majority checking their weight occasionally or rarely (73.8%), and few (7.1%) have ever been medically diagnosed as overweight or obese. Additionally, only 11% report a family history of obesity, suggesting that familial factors may play a minor role in this population

FIGURE 1: Distributions of body image responses by obesity class

TABLE 4.3: EFFECTS OF OBESITY ON BODY IMAGE

VARIABLES		ALWAYS (%)	SOMETIMES (%)	RARELY (%)	NEVER (%)
I FEEL CONFIDENT ABOUT MY BODY	NON-OBESE	72.3	23.9	1.6	2.2
	OBESE	61.5	15.4	7.7	15.4
I FEEL PRESSURE TO LOOK A CERTAIN WAY	NON-OBESE	9.2	34.8	21.2	34.8
	OBESE	15.4	30.8	15.4	38.5
I AVOID CERTAIN CLOTHES BECAUSE OF HOW I LOOK	NON-OBESE	11.4	35.9	16.3	36.4
	OBESE	30.8	19.2	26.9	23.1
MY WEIGHT AFFECTS MY SELF ESTEEM	NON-OBESE	4.3	12.5	14.1	69.0
	OBESE	7.7	23.1	11.5	57.7
I FEEL SELF CONSCIOUS ABOUT MY WEIGHT	NON-OBESE	15.2	26.1	16.8	41.8
	OBESE	23.1	34.6	7.7	34.6
I AVOID SOCIAL GATHERINGS DUE TO CONCERNS ABOUT MY	NON-OBESE	2.7	10.3	6.5	80.4
	OBESE				

WEIGHT

OBESE	0.0	19.2	11.5	69.2
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Table 4.3 Show the clear differences between obese and non-obese students in their perceptions of body image and self esteem. Non-obese undergraduates were more likely to always feel confident about their bodies (72.3%) compared to obese undergraduates (61.5%).

Obese respondents were also more likely to report always feeling pressure to look a certain way (15.4% vs. 9.2%) and to always avoid certain clothes due to body concerns (30.8% vs. 11.4%). With respect to self-esteem, a greater proportion of obese respondents indicated that their weight sometimes affected their self-esteem (23.1% vs. 12.5%). Similarly, more obese respondents reported always feeling self-conscious about their weight (23.1% vs. 15.2%). Social avoidance due to weight concerns was also higher among obese respondents, with 19.2% sometimes avoiding social gatherings compared to 10.3% of non-obese respondents. Overall, obese undergraduates demonstrated more body image concerns, lower confidence, and greater self-consciousness than their non-obese counterparts.

TABLE 4.4: CHI-SQUARE TEST OF ASSOCIATION BETWEEN OBESITY AND BODY IMAGE

VARIABLES	x²	Df	p-value
I FEEL CONFIDENT ABOUT MY BODY	15.05	3	0.0018
I FEEL PRESSURE TO LOOK A CERTAIN WAY	1.43	3	0.6984
I AVOID CERTAIN CLOTHES BECAUSE OF HOW I LOOK	10.67	3	0.0137
MY WEIGHT AFFECTS MY SELF ESTEEM	2.92	3	0.4035
I FEEL SELF CONSCIOUS ABOUT MY WEIGHT	2.99	3	0.3938
I AVOID SOCIAL GATHERINGS DUE TO CONCERNS ABOUT MY WEIGHT	3.45	3	0.3271

Table 4.4 shows that there is obesity is significantly linked to body confidence ($p=0.0018$) and clothing choices ($p=0.0137$). Students with obesity are more likely to feel less confident and avoid certain clothes because of their appearance. Other aspects like pressure to look a certain way, self-esteem, self-consciousness, and social participation showed no significant association($p>0.05$).

TABLE 4.5: COPING MECHANISMS AND SUPPORT SYSTEM

VARIABLES	NEVER(N=26)	RARELY(N=26)	SOMETIMES(N=26)	OFTEN(N=26)
EXERCISING	0(0%)	7(26.9%)	14(53.8%)	5(19.2%)
TALKING TO FRIENDS/FAMILY ABOUT IT	8(30.8%)	8(30.8%)	8(30.8%)	2(7.7%)
AVOIDING SOCIAL SITUATIONS	10(38.5%)	7(26.9%)	7(26.9%)	2(7.7%)
PRAYING OR ENGAGING IN SPIRITUAL ACTIVITIES	9(34.6%)	7(26.9%)	3(11.5%)	7(26.9%)
IGNORING THE ISSUE	11(42.3%)	2(7.7%)	10(38.5%)	3(11.5%)
DIETING	4(15.4%)	4(15.4%)	12(46.2%)	6(23.1%)
SEEKING PROFESSIONAL HELP (COUNSELLOR, THERAPISTS, DOCTOR)	13(50%)	5(19.2%)	8(30.8%)	0(0%)

Table 4.5 shows the findings on coping mechanisms and support systems among obese undergraduates indicate a varied approach to managing obesity-related challenges. Engagement in physical activity and dieting were the most frequently used strategies, with the majority of respondents reporting that they sometimes exercise (53.8%) and diet (46.2%), reflecting efforts to manage body weight.

Spiritual activities were also moderately utilized, with 26.9% engaging often, suggesting a role for personal belief systems. Talking to friends/family was also less applied with only 7.7% reporting frequent use. 11.5% of obese individuals often ignore the issue. Seeking professional help was the least utilized with 50% of participants never accessing such services.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the prevalence of obesity, its effects on body image and coping mechanisms

This chapter draws together and discusses the results of the analysis of the data. The findings are summarized under each research questions and objectives.

5.1 Sociodemographic characteristics

This study included two hundred and ten undergraduates of Osun State University with a mean age of falling within the typical undergraduate age range in Nigeria.

The largest age group was 16-19 years, followed closely by 20-23 years, and then aged 24-27 years. This pattern reflects the early age of entry into higher education and aligns with previous studies, such as (Olatona et al., 2023), who reported that most university students fall within late adolescence and early adulthood; a period where body image concerns are often heightened.

Gender distribution showed that most of the respondents were female, this is similar to findings by (Akinyemi et al., 2025), who observed higher female participation in health surveys and highlighted that female are often more conscious of body image and weight-related issues than males. The absence of respondents identifying as “others” suggests limited gender diversity in this study population.

Regarding academic level, the majority of respondents were in 100 level, followed by 200 level, and 400 level. This distribution indicates a fair representation across levels, with slightly more

participation from first year. Such distribution may reflect accessibility during data collection or higher willingness to participate among lower-level students.

Almost all respondents were single, which is expected given the range and academic commitments of most undergraduates.

Income distributions revealed that most of the respondents earned #10000-#30000. This shows a moderate level of financial support among respondents, which may influence dietary choices and lifestyle behaviours associated with obesity. Previous studies (Olatona et al., 2023) have shown that students with higher allowances may have more access to high calorie fast foods, potentially increasing obesity risk.

5.2 Obesity prevalence

This study found that only a small proportion of respondents were found to be obese. Body image perception was strongly linked to weight status, with students with obesity are more likely to experience body dissatisfaction, self-consciousness, and low self-esteem compared to those with lower BMI.

The high proportion of students who rarely or never checked their weight reflects low awareness of personal health metrics, potentially influencing how they perceive their bodies.

Despite the measured prevalence, only a small number of respondents considered themselves obese, indicating that many undergraduates underestimate their weight status. This misperception can lead to a false sense of body satisfaction among obese students and may delay engagement in weight management behaviours.

Among the respondents, only few of them reported having been diagnosed as overweight or obese by a healthcare professional. This suggests a significant gap in professional screening and counselling among undergraduates. Limited engagement with healthcare professionals may result in missed opportunities for early intervention, nutrition education, and psychological support.

Family history of obesity was reported by few of respondents, which may contribute to heightened body image concerns, especially among those predisposed to weight gain. Students aware of hereditary risk may either greater anxiety about their body image or adopt early preventive measures to avoid similar outcomes.

5.3 The effects of obesity on body image

The analysis shows that body image perception differs between obese and non-obese students, but only certain aspects show statistically significant associations. The bivariate analysis revealed that obese students reported lower confidence in their body image and higher level of clothing avoidance, self-consciousness, and weight-related concerns compared to non-obese students. It collectively revealed the clear differences in body image between obese and non-obese students. It shows that obesity is closely linked with negative body image perceptions, influencing how students view themselves, dress and interact socially.

The chi-square test confirmed that body confidence and clothing avoidance are significantly associated with obesity. Other factors, including pressure to look a certain way, self-esteem, self-consciousness, and avoidance of social gatherings, showed differences descriptively but not statistical significance.

These results indicate that obesity has a measurable impact on body confidence and clothing choices, while its influence on other aspects of body image, though visible in descriptive trends, was not statistically validated in this study.

5.4 Coping mechanisms and support system

Among obese respondents, exercise and dieting were the most common coping strategies for managing concerns about body image, with fifty-three-point eight percent sometimes exercising and almost half of the obese students sometimes dieting. This suggests that obese students attempt to improve their body appearance through lifestyle changes. However, only few of them reported exercising often, showing that weight control efforts are not consistently maintained.

Talking to friends or family showed more even distribution, in each of the “never,” “rarely,” and “sometimes,” categories. This may indicate limited social support or reluctance to discuss body image issues openly due to stigma or embarrassment. Avoidance of social situations were reported by a smaller proportion, reflecting how negative body perception can reduce social participation.

Seeking professional help was the least common method. This aligns with earlier findings that seven-point one percent has received a medical diagnosis of overweight and obesity, suggesting an underutilization of healthcare services.

These findings highlight that most coping behaviours focus on self-driven methods like exercise and dieting, while professional or social support remains underused. This may affect how effectively students can manage body dissatisfaction and achieve healthy lifestyle changes.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

In this study, BMI was used as a measure of general obesity. Results of this study showed the prevalence of obesity is rising in this population group and thus does not bode well for the burden of non-communicable diseases linked to obesity.

Obesity among undergraduates in Osun State University is associated with not only physical health risks but influences how students view and interact with their bodies.

This study established that obesity significantly affects certain aspects of body image like body confidence and clothing avoidance among undergraduates at Osun State University.

Clearly, there is a gap in education regarding obesity and its effects on body image perception, highlighting the need for target interventions within the university setting.

5.3RECOMMENDATION

- Universities should include obesity awareness and mental health education into student programs to improve knowledge and encourage healthy behaviours.
- Dietary counselling services should be introduced to guide students on balanced eating habits that support a healthy body image.
- Regular fitness initiatives such as exercise sessions and sport programs should be encouraged on campus

- Professional counselling and mental health support should be made accessible to help students manage the psychological impacts of obesity.
- Schools should also organize seminars, workshops, and campaigns to educate students on healthy eating, lifestyle choices and coping strategies for stress related to obesity.
- Schools should provide free or low-cost BMI checks and body composition assessments at the university health centre to promote early detection of obesity.

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APPENDIX ONE

QUESTIONNAIRE

My name is **ADEWOLE ADEBOLA VICTORIA**, a final year public health student of Osun State University conducting this research as part of my academic project. Your honest response will be valuable and will only take a few minutes. Every response will be kept private. Please tick(✓) the option that best applies to you in each section, or write your response out if needed.

TITLE: The prevalence and Impact of Obesity on the Psychological Status of Undergraduates in Osun State University, Main Campus, Osogbo

SECTION A: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

1. Age:(in years, as at your last birthday):_____
2. Gender: (a)Male (b)Female (c)others
3. Department: _____
4. Level of Study: (a)100 (b) 200 (c) 300 (d) 400 (e) Others
5. Do you have any medical condition (e.g., diabetes, hypertension)? (a) Yes (b) No (c) Prefer not to say
6. Marital status: (a) Single (b) married (c) others
7. what is your average monthly allowance or monthly income: (a) less than #10000 (b) #10000 to #30000 (b) #31000 to #50000 (b) Above #50000

SECTION B: OBESITY RELATED INFORMATION

8. Height (in m): _____

9. Weight (in kg): _____

10. BMI: _____

11. How often do you check your weight? (a)weekly (b) monthly (c)occasionally (d)rarely (e) never

12. Do you consider yourself obese? (a)Yes (b) No

13. Have you ever tried to lose weight? (a)Yes (b)No

14. Have you ever been diagnosed as overweight or obese by a healthcare professional?(a) Yes(b) No

15. Do you have any family history of obesity? (a)Yes (b) No

16. Do you engage in regular physical activity? (a)Yes (b)No

17. Which physical activity do you engage in ? a)walking (b) running (c) swimming (d) none (e) others (specify)_____

18. How often do you consume fast food or junk food? (a) Daily (b)3–5 times a week (c) 1–2 times a week (d)Rarely (e)Never

19. How many meals do you eat per day? (a)1 (b)2 (c) 3 (d)More than 3

20. How many hours of sleep do you get per night? (a) Less than 4 (b) 4–6 hours (c) 7–9 hours (d) More than 9

21. Do you follow a healthy diet (e.g. fruits, vegetables, whole grains)? (a) Yes (b) No

SECTION C: PSYCHOLOGY RELATED INFORMATION

22. Have you ever experienced discrimination or bullying due to your weight? (a) Yes (b) No

23. Do concerns about your weight affect your ability to concentrate or perform in school? (a) Yes (b) No

24. Have you ever sought psychological support or counselling due to concerns related to your weight? (a) Yes (b) No

Below are questions about body image. Please tick one option for each statement

S/N	STATEMENT	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
25	I feel confident about my body				
26	I feel pressure to look a certain way				
27	I avoid certain clothes because of how I look				
28	My weight affects my self esteem				

29	I feel self conscious about my weight				
30	I avoid social gatherings due to concerns about my body size				

How much do you agree with these statements

S/N	STATEMENT	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
31.	In most way, my life is ideal					
32.	I am satisfied with my life					

SECTION D: COPING MECHANISMS AND SUPPORT SYSTEMS

What strategies do you use to manage your weight and psychological well-being? Please tick one option for each statement

S/N	STRATEGY	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
33	Exercising				

34	Talking to friends/family about it				
35	Avoiding social situations				
36	Praying or engaging in spiritual activities				
37	Ignoring the issue				
38	Dieting				
39	Seeking professional help (counsellor, therapists, doctor)				

40. Do you think there is enough awareness about obesity and its psychological impact among students? (a)Yes (b)No

41.What recommendations do you have for improving obesity awareness and mental health support in your university? _____

APPENDIX TWO

BUDGET

S/N	Item	Amount per Unit (₦)	Unit	No. of Persons	Total Amount (₦)
1	Printing of Questionnaires	100	210 copies	1	21000
2	Physical meetings with supervisor	1000	10	1	10000
3	HREC Forms	1600	1	1	1600
4	Weight scale	20000	1	1	20,000
5	Communication (Calls & Internet) for research	10000	Lump sum	1	10,000
6	Project proposal printing	2000	5	1	10000
7	Measuring tape	4000	1	1	4000
8	Printing and binding of internal and external reports	15000	Lump sum	1	15,000
9	Printing and Binding of Final reports	7000	3	1	21,000

Total = ~~₦~~112,600

Figure 2: Undergraduate being weighed during BMI measurements

Figure 3: Participant's weight check as part of obesity assessment exercise

